

Designing Working Environment Embodied with Emotional and Intimate Communication

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Abstract

In Taiwan, a region with the longest working hours in Asia and rapid development of information technology, people in the same working environment are either closely grouped or further isolated by the chosen web-based communication media. The traditional in-person social interactions between colleagues are disappearing. In this research, the fundamental and emotional needs of coworkers are investigated by interviews and probe diaries. And with the concepts brought out by the workshop with participants, prototypes as communication installation with intimate interface are conceived for various working space to mediate people's informational communication and to evoke the emotional contact between colleagues in an office.

Keywords: Shared Communication, Social Computing, Awareness, Social Interaction, Intimate Interface, Participatory Design, Probe Diaries, Field Trials

Introduction

The structures of community are acutely changing, and people who are working in a contemporary office are facing the rapid development of information technology and new workflows. In Taiwan, a region with the longest working hours in Asia, social interactions between colleagues are disappeared since most of the communications related to the works are shifting from in-person conversation to mediated e-mail through the internet. This makes people in the same working environment either closely grouped or further isolated by the chosen media. Gradually, the daily communications take place in the virtual information space, rather than in a real working space.

In a modern society like Taiwan, people get used to and adore some kind of life style. That brings a distance between people which is by and by disappeared, and a sense of presence with their friends or families becomes irrelevant to their embodied sensation since the new media through the internet achieved by the emerging technology already changes their intercourse manner. Besides, this artificial presence not only symbolizes an equidistant perception of one from others but neutralizes the people's inherent recognition of distance (Moles, 1988).

Meanwhile, those opulent accessible sources of communication and interaction much surpass what people probably use in their whole life, and overflow people's work place or home environment. People start getting used to communicate depending on those new media, such as the e-mail, messenger, or mobile phone. An unexpected phenomenon comes out from the advent of novel communication devices, and people become standoffish and unsociable since they turn into grouped or isolated by habitually using media. Even in a closed workplace, the different usages of intercourse media could estrange people from their coworkers, and relationship between those colleagues is frailer than the days they had some kind of embodied touch or conversations.

In the case of R&D department in high-tech companies, those engineers get huge stress and work at fast tempo, and the boundary of work and leisure blurs and disappears. Besides, the division of labour is explicit, the project cooperation sometimes means to hold a team discussion a week, but for the most part the engineers could finish his work independently. The airy interactions of coworkers are not too much, and connections between the colleagues are quite slight (Diani, 1986; Tang, 2001).

It is believed as a fundamental need of humans to contact with others. Moreover, the interactions and relationships with others are expected not only to make humans consoled and satisfied, but enrich humans' life. Recently, a lot research groups are devoted to enlarge the technology possibility to mediate people at remote place by intimate interface or background awareness (Agamanolis, 2002; Patel et al., 2003; Vetere et al., 2005). Extending their research, the intrinsic needs such as subtle significance of presence or concern between people who works in a long period of time together is explored, and it's been tried to conceive an emotional and intimate working environment of technologies and intimate experiences that build, maintain, and enhance the colleagues' relationships in a new way.

For the colleagues become gradually separated from each other, how to promote their relationship is becoming an important issue. Therefore, creating an embodied office environment with sense of emotional presence, intimacy, or closeness is definitely essential to people who work long hours together.

Methods

In this research, the emphasis is placed on the workers in R&D department. The engineers who explore and develop new processing technologies or system programs were selected from Taiwan's high-tech companies. To explore the needs and desires between the occupied high-tech engineers is not easy. The major problem is that the researcher wasn't allowed to enter their actual working offices to do field observation. Most high-tech companies control their personnel's activities in a very high rigid way since the advanced high-tech research and development of a company are needed under the confidential protection. To orientate the restrictions, this research has been conducted alternatively by using dyad interviews (Ireland, 2003), probe diaries (Gaver *et al.*, 1999; Westerlund et al., 2003), workshops with the interviewee of the previous study and many participants from different disciplines, and prototyping scenarios. The completing prototypes as technology probes of field trials have been arranged in those companies to anticipate the value of these unprecedented media and review the unexpected application concepts with the real usage situation.

Exploring

The issues of personal relationship and communicating are involved in different aspects of people's lives, from personal characteristics and life styles to culture. Here, to find out these engineers' communicating context, clear-cut routine activities, and the perception of the

media they use, the complex real situation of their daily lives in various phases was delineated lucidly by two different methods.

Dyad interviews

In the beginning of the research, to catch on the outline of engineers' communicating contexture and routine activities in their working environments, and to have the discussions more brisk, liberal, and delightful, the traditional one-to-one interviews were replaced with dyad interviews. Two participants working in the same company and sharing the same workplace were interviewed as a pair for at least 2 hours. Several topics for these pairs to discuss were given: context of communication between their colleagues, emotional or physical perspectives of the working environments, routine activities of work and leisure, and sentiments of all communicating media they tend to use. In these interviews, the issues were extended with the prompts they gave to each other. These couples of engineers were unrestricted and ardent to share their experiences of communication with others, their work stress, the way to take a break, and the media they chose and were fond of.

Probe Diaries

After the interviews, the outline of the engineers' daily lives has been drawn and some different aspects have also been shown that might influence the interpersonal relationship in their working environment. Since it is forbidden to use a camera, a video, an audio recorder, or any recording device in the high-tech companies to record engineers' lives, the probe diaries were used to perceive the more details about the interactions of the media they used, the colleagues they touched with, and the environment they involved in. The diaries were divided into two parts: the first part was similar to the traditional ethnography diaries that ask the engineers to take down their daily activities and sentiments three times a day; the second part asked the engineers to sketch their working environments including the spaces for work and leisure they may used. After describing the working environment, there are another four points are indicated: the location of a participant and his/her close friends, the actual distance of the map, the places that his/her colleagues may chitchat together, and the places frequently used by him/her or his/her colleagues (Figure 1).

Figure 1, A probe diary includes two parts: one part is for recording the trivial things about what happens in the workplace and how the recorder feels, and the other part is for sketching the environment.

Findings

The dyad interviews and diaries have revealed a great deal of information. Most engineers are strongly engaged in their own work, and they usually work independently and cannot be interrupted. In general, these engineers' working hours and leisure time were much different from each other. Because of formed habits and different work schedules, the ways how they relax are also distinct.

Besides, gender difference is another significant effect upon the social interaction, which is more notable in such high-tech companies with extreme unequal ratios of males and females. The informants mentioned that the female colleagues tended to make friends with others actively, which might conduce to a positive social relationship. But a male colleague seems a bit unconcerned and detached in a working environment.

By integration and analysis of all issues shown in the investigations, the main aspects of the effects on interpersonal interaction could be one's characteristics and customs, and the external restrictions and pressure. In summary, the key factors that influence the social relationship in an office could be categorized into the following six causes:

- personal characteristics
- work stress

- independence of work and leisure activities
- different media usage
- the management style of a boss or leaders
- the ratio of males and females

The relationships among colleagues were deeply influenced by their emotion, the atmosphere of their working environment, and the media they are accessible to. Some of the engineers in this research seem to depend solely and heavily on digital media for communication. At the same time, there were a few engineers who mentioned they still preferred an embodied interaction with colleagues in natural, direct, immediate ways, such as chatting, sharing something, having an afternoon tea break with colleagues, or just passing a note and leaving a message. However, while they did appreciate these kinds of face-to-face communications, contradictorily they complained that face-to-face communicating might interrupt or slow down their work.

Workshop

The workshop is held with the interviewee of the previous study and many participants from different disciplines, including industrial design, computer science, mechanical engineering, and visual communication. To understand the engineer's working cultures, the findings collected from the previous study were given in the beginning as a mind map format. After that, the participants had a brain storming to explore the potential solutions to enhance the interpersonal relationship in such kind of working environment.

The participants from different aspects enriched the design concepts in various ways. Most of the ideas are interesting and delightful, and they could be simply categorized into five categories: beautification and improvement of embodied environment, information change such as a bulletin board or a blog on-line, friendship association to make friends, periodical arrangements of group exercises and special activities, and some company services such as free refreshments provided or a cosy rest room for employees.

Therefore, what may cause a good mood or relieve one's stress and how to support intimate experience without disturbance are the keys to the solution. After integrating these concepts, we picked some ideas which are achievable to be practiced in field trials, and made complete

communicating scenarios.

Prototyping

Following the outcomes of the previous study, some of these designs have been substantiated concepts, and evaluated if they can work meaningfully and improve the relationship among those engineers.

Designs

Those prototypes were followed the concepts out of the workshop and the expectations of engineers explored in the earlier study. Several issues are addressed when these concepts are developed. First of all, the goal of these concepts is to enhance the chatter and interaction behavior between colleagues in a way but not interrupting their work, such as non-real-time communicating. Besides, the quality of rest time is those engineers' major concern. Further, the behavior of sharing, such as a book, photos, a good song or wonderful experiences, with colleagues not only brings colleagues closer, also enriches each others' understanding at the same time. To this end, an emotional and intimate interface is provided to improve their embodied visual environment.

In order to further discover the people's reception and valuation with different types of media, the prototypes were respectively framed as a communicating system on the internet, a digital device, and a non-tech implement in the working environment. The system based on the internet allows people interacting in a virtual space. The digital device provides a virtual and physical mixed space for the users to experiencing on. The non-tech setup plays as a physical platform to have users to communicate on. As following, the three concepts are explained in detail.

Prototype Design 1: *Linking Village* (Figure 2). Linking Village is a cross-platform information sharing system. It integrates common media formats, and users could easily share interesting information and watch the latest news posted by colleagues through the visualized dynamic display on line. The sharing information would be classified into several types, such as sports, entertainments, economy, or experience sharing. Besides, everyone has his own personal icon with information of hobby or association to introduce himself to others.

Figure 2, Linking Village

Prototype Design 2: *Tree of Sound Track* (Figure 3). The tree is planned to be installed at the corner of the tea room, a space where all engineers would use and have a rest. Since everyone's working hours and leisure time is different from others, these engineers might use the tea room without meeting someone else. The main concept of this design is to let people have perception of others by listening to others' sound tracks. Changing the pleasurable experience of listening to sounds of nature with cosy emotion under a tree, this device provides a chance for people to percept the subtle traces left by their colleagues.

This tree with simple contour randomly plays the music and people's emotional voice previously recorded from the same context, such as laughing or cheering. People also could record a message into the tree at the moment, or download the music he/she likes. In addition, there is a bulletin board on the top to reveal the messages colleagues left and the provider of the broadcasting music.

Figure 3, Tree of Sound Track

Prototype Design 3: *Fruity Air* (Figure 4). Fruity Air looks like a cute shrub with ripe fruits moving in the office passages. It is a bidirectional-open cabinet walking from seat to seat. Since a drawer was full of stuffs that people sharing followed by some subjects, for instance travel photos, guidebook, or video tapes, the drawer shining turns from green to orange and attracts more people to take it.

Figure 4, Fruity Air

Testing

To evaluate our design concepts, each prototype was given more than 2 testing scenarios that might happen in the real field for potential users to exam.

In the preliminary estimations, numerous engineers gave us lots of reflections according to the plots of the scenarios and operations of the prototypes. They all like the interfaces of our prototypes at first sight. “Never thought about an interactive music player would appear in the tea room like this. It looks very charming, and the atmosphere there becomes very cosy, cordial, and delightful. The messages left on the board must be very interesting,” one engineer said. The background sounds, messages or stuff sharing on the Tree of Sound Track, Linking Village, and Fruity Air, extend the subjects of a talk and interactions between colleagues. What is most important of all is these interactions with colleagues won’t interrupt their work, but relieve some work stress. Later, these prototypes we designed from on-line program to a daily article will be put into a high-tech company further for field trials, to estimate the influence of them in the actual working environment.

Finding

Through this study, several major findings are concluded. A contented and delightful working environment with a virtual or physical interesting promoter of airy interpersonal interactions could release one's work stress and make the colleagues closer. Besides, most people subconsciously cherish the slow and leisurely communicating ways, such as sharing a book, a special experience, or leaving some messages, which are not pressing but kind and intimate for the coworkers.

Further Works

To use the prototypes as technology probes for recording in field trials is the next step of our study. The estimation of field trials must be eminent. Even if our prototype scenarios now receive nice responses, we still have no idea if they could really enter into these engineers' daily lives. Therefore, we will try to complete these prototypes and have them tested in field for a week to several months.

Conclusions

The interactions and life-style of Taiwanese high-tech engineers are revealed with interviews and probe diaries. Meanwhile, the reasons that cause the colleagues isolation were also explored. Through the participatory design, we tried to bring up several guidelines to improve the interpersonal relationship between colleagues.

Such issues like communicating and interpersonal relationship are involved in many different aspects of people's lives, from personal characteristics to culture, so the research and design work have to consider extensively, not only focus on the operations between people and interfaces of artifacts, but the people's subtle emotional perceptions of their environment, personal connectedness, and the detail limitations that might effect the communicating activities. The study approaches like dyad interviews, probes, and workshops are very efficient to extent and support these social or emotional designs issues.

Even though technology will never replace the physicality and immediacy face-to-face contact (Vetere et al., 2005), there exist different limitations of reality. In fact, technology and artifacts could bring people closely together by sharing with the idea of intimacy, background awareness and their emotions at times. We hope our study could promote the connectedness between people and make people's lives abundant in the future.

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